

Clinical characteristics and prognostic influence of renal dysfunction in heart failure patients with preserved ejection fraction

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Abstract

Background

Renal dysfunction is common in patients with heart failure (HF) and is associated with high mortality. This relationship is well established in HF and reduced ejection fraction (HFREF), however, it is not fully understood in HF and preserved ejection fraction (HFPEF). The aim of this study was to determine the impact of renal dysfunction on all-cause mortality in HFPEF patients and to evaluate the clinical characteristics of patients that deteriorate renal function in the first year of follow-up.

Methods

We evaluated the patients with HFPEF included in the RICA registry. This is a multi-center and prospective cohort study that includes patients admitted for decompensated HF. Estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR), blood urea nitrogen (BUN) and plasma creatinine concentrations were used for renal function assessment at admission and after one year of follow up.

Results

A total of 455 patients (mean age 78±8.1years; 62% women) were included, of whom 265 (58.2%) had eGFR<60mL/min/1.73m². After adjustment for covariates, only lower admission eGFR remained significantly predictive of all-cause mortality (HR 2.97; 95% CI 1.59–5.53). After one year of follow-up 16.6% of patients deteriorated at least 25% of eGFR. These patients were more likely to be diabetic (54.5% vs 42.6%; p=0.039) and had a higher rate of prescription of mineralcorticoid receptor antagonist (MRA) agents (47% vs 23.3%; p<0.001).

Conclusion

Renal dysfunction is frequently associated with HFPEF. eGFR below normal is strongly associated with mortality. Further decline of renal function is frequent especially among diabetic and patients treated with MRA agents.

Keywords

1. [Heart failure](#)
2. [Preserved ejection fraction](#)
3. [Renal dysfunction](#)
4. [Creatinine](#)
5. [Estimated glomerular filtration rate](#)
6. [Blood urea nitrogen](#)